

Optimal Operation of Electric Vehicles to Enhance the Flexibility Provision in Active Distribution Grids

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Motivation & Objective

The **growing penetration** of EVs in residential distribution networks introduces operational challenges but also opens up opportunities for flexibility provision. This work proposes a day-ahead scheduling framework that maximizes EV-based flexibility while ensuring network reliability and user satisfaction.

Flexibility in EV Charging

Traditional flexibility in power systems is assessed in the **PQ plane** (active vs. reactive power capacity). **EVs offer a new dimension** of flexibility based on their State of Charge (SoC) — a sequential time-dependent energy parameter.

A. Minimum SoC curve: Represents the scenario in which charging is postponed until time t_{ev}^L .

$$t_{ev}^L = t_{ev}^{dep} - \frac{T_{ev}^{ch} \cdot (E_{ev}^{min} - E_{ev,t-1})}{P_{ev}}$$

B. Upward flexibility: Is defined as the ability of an EV to increase its charging power during a specific time period.

C. Downward flexibility: Is defined as the ability of an EV to reduce the predetermined charging power.

$$P_{ev,t}^{\uparrow} = \min(\overline{P_{ev}} - P_{ev,t}^{ch}, \frac{\overline{E_{ev}} - E_{ev,t-1}}{\Delta T})$$

$$P_{ev,t}^{\downarrow} = \min(P_{ev,t}^{ch}, \frac{E_{ev,t} - E_{ev,t}^{min}}{\Delta T})$$

- EV driving patterns from surveys (PDFs of arrival, departure, distance)
- EV types assigned probabilistically from EU sales data
- Charging setup: 80% three-phase (11 kW), 20% single-phase (3.7 kW)
- Household loads from smart meter data
- PV profiles based on DSO statistics (rooftop units, uniform irradiance)
- Network: 3 radial feeders, 315 kVA transformer, 30 customers/feeder

Case Study
Details:

Modeling Framework

Two power flow balance constraints must be satisfied at each time step to ensure safe operation:

- 1) For downward flexibility activation ($s = 0$),
- 2) For upward flexibility activation ($s = 1$).

$$\max_{P_{ev,t}^{ch}, P_{s,ev,t}} \sum_{ev \in \Omega_{ev}} \sum_{t \in \Omega_T} \sum_{s \in \Omega_S} C_{s,t} \cdot P_{s,ev,t}$$

s.t. OPF constraints

EV storage constraints

$$P_{s,ev,t} \leq P_{ev,t}^{ch} \quad \text{for } s = 0$$

$$E_{ev,t-1} + (P_{ev,t}^{ch} + P_{s,ev,t}) \cdot \Delta T \leq E_{ev} \quad \text{for } s = 0$$

$$P_{s,ev,t} \leq P_{ev}^{max} - P_{ev,t}^{ch} \quad \text{for } s = 1$$

$$E_{ev,t-1} + (P_{ev,t}^{ch} - P_{s,ev,t}) \cdot \Delta T \geq E_{ev,t}^{min} \quad \text{for } s = 1$$

Results

- Since the discharging function was disabled, the upward flexibility was more prominent, especially during the peak load hours. Moreover, the flexibility increased during the peak load hours.
- The upward flexibility during 18:00-05:00 can increase the transformer loading until it reaches the limits, validating the high-power capabilities of EV chargers.
- The charging process was performed uniformly over time to maximize flexibility.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that increasing EV adoption is likely to have a good potential for LV network management. However, the downward flexibility may not be enough in G2V schemes. In addition, EV flexibility is time-dependent; each action (e.g., upward charging) modifies the SoC and shifts future availability. As a result, the process must be recalculated at every step when flexibility is activated to reflect the updated flexibility state. This remains challenging due to the high computational burden of solving such OPF problems in real time.

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